

Book Review by Jagdish Batra

Who is raising your children?

Rajiv Malhotra and Vijaya Viswanathan

BlueOne Ink, Noida

431+lxxxiv

Rs. 699

NEP 2020 and the International Tantra

NEP2020 is all over the academic world and beyond in the minds of concerned parents of children – young and old, and of course, the students themselves at the receiving end. While most reactions coming from different quarters have been favourable, there are certain disturbing features towards which the book *Who is raising your children?* draws our attention.

Author Rajiv Malhotra, a well-known Indologist, has published fourteen books, focusing mainly to correct the biased approaches of western intellectuals towards Indian culture. Based in the US, he founded Infinity Foundation through which he has distributed 400 grants to various educational bodies to further India-specific programmes. His associate and co-author Vijaya Viswanathan works to develop curricula and pedagogies according to Indian civilizational values.

We have had some critics within India, who found the NEP2020 document to be a carbon copy of the pattern followed at an American university, even as they glossed over its emphasis on native languages and Indian knowledge system. However, Malhotra and Viswanathan, in their non-fiction work *Who is raising your children?*, have highlighted the role that the vested international (read Western) interests have played through forums like the UNO, WHO, etc. in secretly orientating complacent governments into incorporating their agenda. A recent example was the signing of the draft agreement regarding pandemic which gives unbridled power to the WHO in the matter of declaring and managing epidemics in the world – at least in the signatory countries that include India.

The writer-duo find the Sustainable Development Goals 2030 guiding the NEP2020 objectives. While the goals by themselves do not raise heckles, it is the politics behind it – largely orchestrated

by the Woke Left in collaboration with what has come to be known as the Deep State of America – that causes concern. At stake are not only the future upbringing of our children and youth, but also the future of India and its sovereignty.

The book deals in detail the twin planks of Social Emotional Learning and Comprehensive Sex Education – the philosophy and the pedagogy of these areas of teaching/learning. Conforming to the Woke ideology, the programmes are meant to break gender norms of society and make gender a matter of choice for young people. The philosophy behind it is the concept of fluid identity which is currently high on the syllabi of learners in our colleges and universities. So, it is not merely the study but also practice that is sought to be encouraged and supported at school level. One remembers how Elon Musk had bemoaned the ‘death’ of his son, who had, in fact, changed his gender and turned into daughter, while still in school and without the knowledge of Musk himself.

Sex education is oriented towards learning more of the 52 shades of gender rather than giving the pupils knowledge of reproduction and health. Queer ideology seeks to queer the straight ones among pupils in the name of liberty and diversity. Again, this new avatar of sex education abets practice also in “high-risk sexual behaviour with ‘how to’ guides on masturbation, anal sex, etc. In case of any complication, the support system is made available and the students are taught that abortion and queering are normal. These are the ‘sexual rights’ that are to be enshrined among human rights in the time to come!

The author duo reveal the pedophilic tendencies of Queer theorists which explains the attempt at treating pedophilia as the Adult-Young Relationship and thus, destigmatizing and decriminalizing it. It is indeed worrisome to note that the young pupils in schools are sought to be turned into activists of sorts in place of learning basic numeracy and literacy. The Marxist approach divides students in classrooms into oppressors and oppressed on the basis of what their ancestors supposedly did!

The Marxist ideal of redistribution of wealth has also found takers among the oligarchs in the western world. Their worldview is that the middle class bourgeois will be squeezed out and the super-rich oligarchs will then control the working class (whatever is left after depopulation drive) through the use of AI. There is the Brave New World for you!

The authors also take up other items of the Woke ideology, namely DEI. It is common knowledge now that Diversity and Inclusivity mean acknowledging the rights of the minorities and LGBTQ++ communities, but to fetishize them at the expense of the majority in the world would not be justified. Equity is under attack because of its focus on equality of outcome rather than on meritocracy and providing help to the dispossessed at the preparatory stage. Trump administration’s tirade against the Woke activists and Left-wing activists on university campuses should satisfy the authors.

The book is well researched indicated by forty-five pages of Bibliography appended. A number of thinkers and advocates of current ideologies, apart from several case studies find mention in the book. There are sixteen pages devoted to appendices. Graphic charts have been liberally provided to make things clear. There is however quite a bit of repetition of ideas which shows the production of the book was done under pressure of time. Also, one misses the summaries at the end of chapters which we normally find in Rajiv Malhotra’s books.

Malhotra has been criticized as a right-wing nationalist, a conspiracy theorist, etc., but such epithets should not cloud our assessment of his views. This book has been termed as “an urgent wake-up call exposing the hidden threats to India’s future generation” by renowned author Madhu Kishwar. Indeed, NEP2020 is set to shape the future of our children and it concerns all Indians to be aware of

the fingerprint and do our bit to lead the education revolution along the right path so that the nation does not become subservient to foreign forces through a different route. That's surely for the sake of our own future which consideration makes the book worth-reading.

***Jagdish Batra is Professor Emeritus of English at SRM University Delhi-NCR. Email: drjagdishbatra@gmail.com**